

PHASE STABILITY OF Ti(C_{1-x}N_x) SOLID SOLUTION USING AB-INITIO CALCULATION

J. Kim¹, S. Kang^{1*}

¹ Department of Material Science and Engineering, Seoul National University, Seoul 151-744, Korea

* Corresponding author(Shinkang@Snu.ac.kr)

Keywords: Phase stability, Solid solution, ab-initio calculation, formation Gibbs free energy

Abstract

The phase stability of Ti(C_{1-x}N_x) solid solutions was investigated based on the first principle calculations. The Debye model and the rigid band model was employed to calculate the free energy of Ti(C_{1-x}N_x) solid solutions at zero and finite temperature. As a tool of the first principle calculations, we used VASP (Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package). The Gibbs free energy of formation was obtained from the results of first principle calculations and the standard state energies of pure titanium, graphite and nitrogen. The composition near the nitrogen content (x) 0.6, was showed the highest phase stability at 1783 K (= 1510 °C). The phase stability of Ti(C_{1-x}N_x) solid solution was divided into three regions; nitride stable, intermediate and carbide stable region. This result is able to provide the prediction that which composition is decomposed (or formed) faster or slower compared to the other Ti(C_{1-x}N_x) solid solution compositions at given experiment condition.

1 Introduction

Phase stability and mechanical properties of Ti(C_{1-x}N_x) solid solutions represent an important issue in the area of Ti(C,N)-based solid solution cutting-tools. Compared to the mechanical properties, most parts of the phase stability of Ti(C,N) solid solutions have been veiled [1-3].

In liquid phase sintering, the phase stability is very important factor affecting to the microstructure and the mechanical properties of the tool materials. Because, the phase stability implies dissolution behavior of certain carbide phase at the given experimental conditions and dissolution is critical factor to determine the microstructure of the cutting tool materials.

In the present research the free energy of mixing for Ti(C_{1-x}N_x) solid solution carbo-nitrides was

calculated using quasi-harmonic Debye approximation and VASP (Vienna ab initio simulation package) calculation results [4 - 6]. To calculate the free energy of solid solution materials, we employed ideal and modified-ideal solid solution models.

2 Approach

2.1 General settings

In order to understand the phase stability of Ti(C,N) solid solution materials, an accurate calculation of Gibbs free energy of formation is required. Gibbs free energy of formation implies many thermodynamic quantities, i.e. the enthalpy of mixing, the configurational entropy of mixing, the electronic free energy of mixing and the vibrational entropy of mixing. To determine Gibbs free energy of certain composition at the given conditions, non-equilibrium Gibbs free energy was used,

$$G^*(x, P, T) = E(x) + PV(x) + A_{vib}(x, T)$$

where x is configuration factor, E(V) is the total energy per unit cell, PV represents the external pressure term and A_{vib} is the vibrational Helmholtz free energy given the Debye approximation. The vibrational Helmholtz free energy is able to write as

$$A_{vib}(\theta, T) = nK_b T \left[\frac{9\theta}{8T} + 3 \ln \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\theta}{T}} \right) - D \left(\frac{\theta}{T} \right) \right]$$

where θ is the Debye temperature, n is the number of atoms per formula unit and $D \left(\frac{\theta}{T} \right)$ is the Debye integral defined as

$$D(y) = 3/y \int_0^y \frac{x^3}{e^x - 1} dx$$

The Debye temperature θ is obtained by

$$\theta_D = \frac{\hbar}{k} [6\pi^2 V^{1/3} n]^{1/2} f(\sigma) \sqrt{\frac{B_s}{M}}$$

where M is the molecular mass of the crystal, $f(\sigma)$ is given by

$$f(\sigma) = [3\{2(\frac{2}{3} \frac{1+\sigma}{1-2\sigma})^{\frac{3}{2}} + (\frac{1}{3} \frac{1+\sigma}{1-\sigma})^{\frac{3}{2}}\}^{-1}]^{1/3}$$

where σ is Poisson's ratio and B_s is the adiabatic bulk modulus which is approximately calculated using the static compressibility⁴¹

$$B_s \approx B(V) = V \left[\frac{d^2 E(V)}{dV^2} \right]$$

In addition in the present theoretical calculations, thermal electron excitation contribution is also considered. The thermal electron excitation contribution on the Gibbs free energy is able to express to

$$H_{el}(T, V) = N \int_0^{\infty} n(\varepsilon, V) f(\varepsilon) \varepsilon d\varepsilon - N \int_0^{\varepsilon_F} n(\varepsilon, V) \varepsilon d\varepsilon$$

$$S_{el} = -Nk_B \int_0^{\infty} n(\varepsilon, V) [f \ln f + (1-f) \ln(1-f)] d\varepsilon$$

where H_{el} is enthalpy of the electronic excitation, S_{el} is entropy of the electronic excitation, f is Fermi-Dirac distribution. And Fermi energy E_F is calculated by

$$E_F = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{3\pi^2 N}{V} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}}$$

where N is the number of free electrons and $n(\varepsilon, V)$ can be expressed by

$$n(\varepsilon, V) = \frac{dN}{d\varepsilon} = \frac{V}{2\pi^2} \left(\frac{2m}{\hbar^2} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \varepsilon^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

To calculate zero temperature properties of the solid solution materials VASP (Vienna ab initio simulation package) was employed in the present theoretical calculations [5,6]. To use VASP, model has to be defined, therefore unit- and super-cell (2 x 2 x 1 and 2 x 2 x 2) models were used (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Unit- and super-cell models of TiC (Fm-3m, No. 225) material: (a) Unit-cell, (b) (2 x 2 x 1) super-cell and (c) (2 x 2 x 2) super-cell models: White balls indicate Ti (metal) and gray balls indicate C (non-metal), respectively.

Exchange-correlation effects were treated in the framework of the generalized gradient approximation (GGA). Integration in the Brillouin zone was performed using the Monkhorst Pack 11 x 11 x 11 and 9 x 9 x 9 k-points for the unit cell, 5 x 5 x 5 and 7 x 7 x 14 k-points for the super cell model of B1 and hexagonal structures, respectively. To improve the accuracy of the results, we employed a high energy cutoff of 500, 550 eV and an energy convergence of 0.01 eV/Ans. A fully relaxed model structure was obtained by performing more than three times structure optimization calculations for each composition.

2.2 Thermodynamic solid solution models

Two thermodynamic models are considered in the present calculations. These are ideal-, modified ideal- and real-solution models. The first, if solid solution shows ideal solid solution behavior, Gibbs free energy of mixing is able to express as

$$\Delta G^M = \Delta H^M - T\Delta S^M$$

Also, ideal solution means there is no interaction between original and foreigner atoms,

$$\Delta H^M = 0,$$

And the ΔS^M is able to write as following equation.

$$\Delta S^M = \Delta S^M_{\text{thermal}} + \Delta S^M_{\text{configuration}}$$

As a definition, $\Delta S^M_{\text{configuration}}$ is expressed as

$$\Delta S^M_{\text{configuration}} = RT(X_A \ln(X_A) + X_B \ln(X_B) + X_C \ln(X_C) + \dots)$$

and $\Delta S^M_{\text{thermal}}$ can be calculated from theoretical calculations.

However in real situation, it is impossible to ignore the interaction between original and foreigner atoms. Therefore to close the real situation we have to consider the interaction of atoms ΔH^M . As a respect of deviation from the ideal solution, the system with non-zero ΔH^M means the system deviates from ideal solution the amount of absolute ΔH^M . As a result, modification factor is able to employ in the solid solution models. The modification factor is expressed by

$$\delta = \exp \left[-\frac{|\Delta H^M|^n}{RT} \right], (n \geq 0, \text{Avitery value})$$

$$\Delta S^M_{\text{conf.}}^{\text{Mod.}} = \delta \Delta S^M_{\text{conf.}}^{\text{ideal}}$$

where, δ is modification factor, R is gas constant, T is absolute temperature and $\Delta S^M_{\text{conf.}}^{\text{Mod.}}$ is configurational entropy of modified solution system.

3 Results and discussion

To obtain thermodynamic properties of Ti(C,N) solid solution materials, present theoretical calculations adopted two solid solution models. These are ideal and modified-ideal solid solution models. Figure 2 shows Gibbs free energy variation of TiC (B1), TiN(B1), WC(B1) and WC (Hex.) from first-principle calculations and other theoretical considerations. Compared to experimental results⁶⁰ the calculation results are highly accurate except high temperature range. This reflects limitation of quasi-harmonic approximation theory in high temperature range. The calculations using GGA and LDA exchange-correlation functional were conducted however results from the calculations

using GGA exchange-correlation functional yielded more accurate data compared to experimental data.

Fig. 2. Calculated Gibbs free energy of TiC, TiN, WC (B1) and WC (Hex.) materials at different temperatures: (a) TiC, (b) TiN

Consequently, the present theoretical calculations uses only the calculation results from the GGA exchange-correlation functional. To understand thermodynamic properties of Ti(C,N) solid solution materials Gibbs free energy of mixing have to be obtained, firstly.

The Gibbs free energy of mixing represents solution behavior compared to ideal solid solution materials. Figure 3 shows that the Gibbs free energy of mixing (ΔG^M) of $Ti(C_{1-x}N_x)$ solid solution materials with respect to solid solution models. Comparing to ideal solid solution, the other solid solution models show a negative deviation. It indicates that mixing tendency of TiC and TiN is strong in Ti(C,N) solid solution materials. Results using the modified ideal-solution model is getting closer as increasing of n value in equation of the modified ideal- solution model because increasing the n value means decreasing the effect of mixing enthalpy on mixing entropy. This result is in good agreement with previous results.^{8,9}

Fig. 3. Gibbs free energy of mixing (ΔG^M) of the $Ti(C_{1-x}N_x)$ solid solution materials with respect to three kinds of solid solution models (Ideal-, modified ideal- (n = 0.1, 0.5, 1) and real solid

solution models) at 298.15 and 1783 K: (a) 298.15 K and (b) 1783 K.

Figure 4 illustrates Gibbs free energy of formation change at different temperature as a function of nitrogen content x . The results show that as increases nitrogen content x , formation Gibbs free energies are decreased. It indicates that the phase stability of Ti(C,N) solid solution materials increase with nitrogen content. This reflects higher phase stability of TiN than that of TiC in low temperature range. However, phase stability of TiN is steeply decreased as increasing temperature. At 1500 K, phase stability of Ti(C,N) solid solutions has a minimum value of the formation Gibbs free energy at intermediate composition near the TiN (Fig. 4 (b)). Above this temperature, as increasing temperature Ti(C,N) solid solution composition having minimum formation energy shifts from nitrogen rich to carbon rich region. Finally, TiC has the lowest phase stability at 3000 K (Fig. 4 (c)).

Fig. 4. Formation Gibbs free energy of $Ti(C_{1-x}N_x)$ solid solution materials at different temperatures.

4 Summary

The present calculations demonstrated that Ti(C,N) solid solutions have negative deviation compared to ideal solid solution model. The phase stability of Ti(C,N) solid solutions investigated and the nitrogen rich solid solution materials have higher stability than that of the carbon rich solid solution materials in low temperature range. This result was originated from high stability of TiN in low temperature range. At 1500 K, phase stability of Ti(C,N) solid solutions had a minimum value of the formation Gibbs free energy at intermediate composition near the TiN. Above this temperature, as increasing temperature Ti(C,N) solid solution composition having minimum formation energy changed from nitrogen rich to carbon rich region. Finally, TiC was the most stable phase at 3000 K.

All of the present results were in good agreement with previous experimental and theoretical data and using this theoretical methods in other Ti-based solid solution materials will provide good insights to understand the other Ti-based solid solution materials.

5 References

- [1] N. Liu, S. Chao and X. Huang "Effects of TiC/TiN addition on the microstructure and mechanical properties of ultra-fine grade Ti(C,N)-Ni cermets" *J. Euro. Ceram. Soc.* Vol. 26, pp 3861-3870, 2006.
- [2] N. Liu, X. Liu, X. Zhang and L. Zhu "Effect of carbon content on the microstructure and mechanical properties of superfine Ti(C,N)-based cermets" *Mater. Charact.* Vol. 59, pp 1440-1446, 2008.
- [3] J. Kim, S. Ahn and S. Kang "Effect of the complete solid-solution phase on the microstructure of Ti(CN)-based cermet" *Int. J. Refract. Met. Hard Mater.* Vol. 27, pp 224-228, 2009.
- [4] M. Blanco, E. Francisco and V. Luana "Gibbs: isothermal-isobaric thermodynamics of solids from energy curves using a quasi-harmonic Debye model" *Comput. Phys. Commun.* Vol. 158, pp 57-72, 2004.
- [5] G. Kresse and J. Hafner "Ab initio molecular-dynamics simulation of the liquid-metal-amorphous-semiconductor transition in germanium" *Phys. Rev. B* Vol. 49, pp 14251, 1994.
- [6] G. Kresse J. Furthmuller, "Efficient iterative schemes for ab initio total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set" *Phys. Rev. B* Vol. 54, pp 11169, 1996.